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Research Consortium Archive

P(ISSN) : 3007-0031

E(ISSN) : 3007-004X

<https://rc-archive.com/index.php/Journal/about>

Migraine, Mental Health, and Academic Success: Exploring the Triple Interaction Among University Students

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Publisher : EDUCATION GENIUS SOLUTIONS

Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review

ABSTRACT

Migraines are a prevalent neurological disorder that frequently co-occur with psychiatric conditions such as anxiety, depression, and stress, leading to substantial functional impairment and reduced quality of life. University students are particularly vulnerable, as the combined burden of migraines and mental health challenges may negatively impact academic performance, including concentration, exam attendance, and grade point averages. This cross-sectional study investigated the prevalence of migraines, psychiatric symptoms, and their association with academic performance among 412 students from FATA University, Dara Adam Kheel, Kohat and Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar. Data were collected using validated instruments, including the Migraine Disability Assessment (MIDAS), ID-Migraine Test, Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7), Patient Health Questionnaire-4 (PHQ-4), and a custom academic impact questionnaire. Results indicated that 28.5% of students experienced migraines, with 68% reporting moderate-to-severe disability. Anxiety, depression, and stress were reported by 32%, 28.9%, and 26% of participants, respectively, and co-occurrence with migraines significantly increased the odds of academic disruption. Stress, sleep deprivation, and academic workload were the most frequently reported migraine triggers. Students with migraines reported reduced concentration (56%), missed exams (42%), GPA decline (61%), and difficulty completing assignments (59%). The findings underscore the need for early screening, targeted mental health interventions, stress management programs, and academic accommodations to support students' well-being and academic success.

Keywords: Migraine, University Students, Mental Health, Anxiety, Depression, Stress, Academic Performance, Migraine Disability, Aura

Introduction

Migraine is a primary neurological headache disorder characterized by unilateral, pulsating pain of moderate to severe intensity, often aggravated by routine physical activity and accompanied by associated symptoms such as nausea, photophobia, or phonophobia (Headache Classification Committee of the International Headache Society (IHS, 2018). Globally, migraine is recognized as one of the most disabling disorders, significantly contributing to reduced quality of life, functional impairment, and economic burden due to decreased productivity and increased healthcare utilization (Vos et al., 2020; Steiner et al., 2018). Beyond the physical manifestations, a growing body of evidence indicates that migraines are strongly associated with various mental health conditions, particularly anxiety, stress, and depression (Bergman-Bock, 2017; Breslau et al., 1991; Breslau & Davis, 1993; Irimia et al., 2021; Oedegaard et al., 2006; Wacogne et al., 2003). Psychiatric

comorbidities can exacerbate both the frequency and intensity of migraine attacks, often creating a cyclical interaction whereby migraine pain worsens psychological distress and vice versa, thereby amplifying the overall disability burden (Breslau et al., 1991; Irimia et al., 2021).

The prevalence of migraine is particularly high among student populations, including university and medical students, who are subject to unique stressors such as academic pressure, high cognitive demands, irregular sleep patterns, and social adaptation challenges (Birkie et al., 2021; Rafi et al., 2022; Szabó et al., 2024). These factors not only increase vulnerability to migraine attacks but also exacerbate underlying psychiatric symptoms, creating a multidimensional impact on students' mental and physical well-being (Acharya et al., 2018; Mahmoud et al., 2012; Zivin et al., 2009). Several studies indicate that students with migraines report higher levels of anxiety, depression, and perceived stress, suggesting that mental health challenges may both precipitate and result from recurrent migraine episodes. Moreover, the burden of migraine is often compounded by limited awareness, delayed diagnosis, and inadequate management strategies, including over-reliance on over-the-counter analgesics without professional consultation (Rafi et al., 2022; Birkie et al., 2021).

Migraine-related disability represents a critical public health and academic concern. Migraines can produce moderate to severe functional limitations, negatively affecting physical activity, cognitive performance, emotional regulation, and social interactions (Pina et al., 2024; Pradeep et al., 2020; Renjith et al., 2016). For university students, this often translates into difficulty maintaining concentration in class, absenteeism, reduced study efficiency, missed deadlines, and diminished academic performance, including lower grade point averages (GPA) (Osman Ali et al., 2022; Szabó et al., 2024). The impact is often compounded when migraines coexist with psychiatric symptoms, as co-occurrence is associated with higher frequency, longer duration, and greater severity of attacks, further impairing academic engagement and overall quality of life (Pradeep et al., 2020; Wacogne et al., 2003). In addition, chronic migraines and migraines with aura are particularly concerning, as these subtypes have been linked to stronger psychiatric comorbidities, higher levels of disability, and greater interference with day-to-day functioning compared to episodic or non-aura migraines (Breslau et al., 1991; Oedegaard et al., 2006).

Despite the well-established associations between migraine, mental health, and academic performance, research exploring their combined effects among university students especially in diverse cultural and educational contexts is limited. Most studies have focused on medical students or narrowly defined populations, leaving a gap in understanding how migraines, psychiatric

symptoms, and academic outcomes interact across broader university settings (Rafi et al., 2022; Szabó et al., 2024). Furthermore, gender differences, lifestyle factors, and socio-economic determinants have been insufficiently examined, despite evidence suggesting that female students and those experiencing financial or social stress may be disproportionately affected (Mahmoud et al., 2012). Understanding how varying levels of migraine severity, frequency, and psychiatric comorbidity influence academic outcomes is critical, as students experiencing both frequent migraines and poor mental health are likely at the greatest risk for impaired learning, delayed progression, and diminished academic success (Oedegaard et al., 2006).

Investigating these interactions is vital not only for individual student well-being but also for university policies and public health planning. Early identification of at-risk students, timely intervention, and integrated support strategies including stress management, counseling services, academic accommodations, and targeted migraine management can mitigate the negative consequences on both mental health and academic performance. Additionally, increasing awareness among students, faculty, and healthcare providers regarding the reciprocal relationship between migraines and mental health is essential for fostering proactive health-seeking behaviors and promoting adaptive coping strategies. Future research should also focus on longitudinal assessment, cross-cultural comparisons, and the biological and psychosocial mechanisms underlying migraine and psychiatric comorbidities, thereby informing evidence-based interventions that enhance both educational outcomes and overall quality of life for students (Osman Ali et al., 2022; Pina et al., 2024).

Correlation between Mental Health and Migraines

A substantial body of evidence indicates that individuals with migraines are at a heightened risk for psychiatric comorbidities, particularly anxiety, stress, and depression (Bergman-Bock, 2017). Although many psychiatric conditions are associated with migraine, the strongest and most frequently reported associations involve mood and anxiety disorders. Stress and anxiety, in particular, are found to be significantly higher in migraine sufferers and are widely recognized as common triggers for migraine attacks (Wacogne et al., 2003).

Research has consistently shown that psychiatric disorders occur more frequently among individuals with migraines when compared to the general population. In a landmark study, Breslau and Davis (1993) examined the relationship between migraines and psychiatric problems in a large random sample of young adults. Their findings revealed that individuals with a history of migraines were substantially more likely to experience lifetime major depression, anxiety disorders, and suicidal behavior. Importantly, participants with migraines were also more inclined to seek mental health services, indicating that the burden of migraine extends

beyond physical symptoms to psychological distress. Moreover, over a follow-up period of 14 months, individuals with pre-existing migraines showed a greater likelihood of developing new-onset major depressive disorder and panic disorder, suggesting that migraines may act as a precursor or risk factor for later psychiatric morbidity (Breslau & Davis, 1993).

Further support for this association comes from an earlier epidemiological study conducted in Detroit, Michigan. Breslau et al. (1991) investigated migraine prevalence and psychiatric disorders in a large community sample. The study found exceptionally high comorbidity rates: approximately 30% of individuals with migraines experienced both major depression and anxiety disorders. Notably, depression rarely appeared without anxiety in the migraine group. Of the individuals who had migraines, major depression, and anxiety disorders simultaneously, a majority experienced anxiety symptoms first, which were then followed by migraine onset and later depression (Breslau et al., 1991). Logistic regression demonstrated that migraines increased the risk of major depression threefold, and the combination of migraine plus anxiety increased the risk nearly twenty-three times compared to individuals without either condition. The authors also highlighted that migraine with aura was associated with even higher rates of psychiatric disorders than migraine without aura (Breslau et al., 1991).

The distinction between migraine with aura and without aura has been further supported by subsequent research. A large-scale study from the Norwegian Nord-Trøndelag Health Survey (HUNT) involving more than 49,000 participants found that women with migraine with aura had significantly higher rates of depression and anxiety when compared to women without aura (Oedegaard et al., 2006). Women with aura exhibited a 1.7-fold increased risk of depression and a 1.6-fold increased risk of combined anxiety and depression. However, among men, no significant associations were observed between migraine subtype and anxiety or depression (Oedegaard et al., 2006).

The severity and frequency of migraines also play a crucial role in determining the intensity of psychiatric symptoms. Irimia et al. (2021), using data from the Spanish Migraine Atlas Survey, found that the number of monthly headache days was positively associated with depression, anxiety, disability, and reduced quality of life. According to their findings, even moderate migraine frequency (3-14 days per month) significantly increased anxiety symptoms, while chronic migraine (15 or more days per month) was linked to sharply elevated levels of depression. This suggests that migraine frequency is a critical factor not only in physical disability but also in psychological burden.

Consistent with these findings, Wacogne et al. (2003) also identified stress and anxiety as central psychological dimensions of migraine. Their study reported that individuals with migraines

experienced higher levels of everyday stress, intrusive thoughts, fatigue, irritability, and pressure. Stress emerged as the most prominent and consistent trigger for migraine attacks, confirming its significant role in exacerbating migraine symptoms. While depression was less likely to act as a trigger, it frequently developed after the onset of migraine episodes, indicating that chronic migraine pain may contribute to the development or worsening of depressive symptoms.

Prevalence of Mental Health Issues Among University Students

University students often experience significant mental health challenges as they transition into academically demanding and socially complex environments. Mahmoud et al. (2012) conducted a study among 508 full-time U.S. college students aged 18-24 and found high rates of depression (29%), anxiety (27%), and stress (24%). Among students experiencing anxiety, 67% also had depression, and 61% reported high stress. The study further highlighted that students with ineffective coping strategies experienced significantly more depression and anxiety, and those with higher distress levels were more dissatisfied with their lives. Additionally, lower GPAs were associated with increased depressive symptoms, underscoring the relationship between mental health and academic performance (Mahmoud et al., 2012).

Acharya et al. (2018) reported similar findings in their analysis of stressors and depressive symptoms among 631 U.S. college students, including domestic and international students. Their results indicated that 46.94% of participants showed moderate to severe depression symptoms, with females and international students experiencing higher rates. Key stressors included changes in social interactions, unfamiliar environments, disruption of eating and sleeping routines, academic workload, and low grades.

Mental health problems among college students not only emerge but also persist over time. Zivin et al. (2009) conducted a longitudinal study involving 2,843 undergraduate and graduate students during an initial survey in 2005, followed by 763 students who completed the survey again in 2007. More than half of these students experienced at least one mental health issue, and 60% continued to face mental health difficulties two years later. Despite the persistence of these concerns, fewer than half of the students sought professional care, indicating a substantial treatment gap in university settings.

Academic stress also contributes significantly to students' mental and physical well-being. MacGeorge et al. (2005) examined the effects of emotional and informational support on the relationship between academic stress, depression, and physical health among college students from two eastern U.S. universities. Their findings revealed a positive association between academic stress and both depression and physical symptoms, suggesting that academic pressure can simultaneously affect psychological and

physical health.

Prevalence of Migraines Among University Students

Migraines are increasingly recognized as a major health concern among college populations. Rustom et al. (2022) conducted a large study at the University of Sharjah involving 569 students aged 17-25 from various academic disciplines. Among these students, 464 reported experiencing headaches in the previous year, and 150 met the diagnostic criteria for migraines. This indicated a migraine prevalence rate of 26.35%. According to MIDAS scores, 60% of migraine sufferers experienced moderate to severe disability. Alarmingly, most students self-medicated with non-migraine-specific over-the-counter analgesics, indicating insufficient awareness and limited use of medical services.

Similarly, a study by Rafi et al. (2022) in Bangladesh found a migraine prevalence of 21.4% among university students, with female students showing particularly higher rates (29%) compared to males (12%). Furthermore, 68% of participants reported experiencing more than five migraine attacks in the past month, and 57.5% reported frequent analgesic use. Despite the severity and frequency of symptoms, only 42% had consulted a medical professional in the previous year, highlighting another treatment gap.

In Ethiopia, Birkie et al. (2021) reported an even higher migraine prevalence of 34% among undergraduate students at Wollo University. The study included 371 participants with diverse socio-demographic backgrounds. Students with a prior history of migraines were 3.83 times more likely to experience recurrent migraine attacks. The researchers suggested that academic pressure, inadequate rest, and lifestyle factors may further exacerbate migraine vulnerability among university students.

Correlation Between Mental Health and Migraines Among Students

University students who experience anxiety, stress, or depression are more likely to suffer from migraines. For instance, Rafi et al. (2022) reported that students with anxiety had a 34% prevalence of migraines, compared to only 16% among students without anxiety. Similarly, students with depression had a 29% likelihood of experiencing migraines, while those without depression had only 16%. Stress emerged as the most common trigger, affecting 71% of students in the study. Furthermore, students with anxiety were found to have 2.35 times higher odds of having migraines than their peers without anxiety, highlighting the significant role of mental health in the occurrence of migraines among university students (Rafi et al., 2022).

Similarly, Rustom et al. (2022) examined common triggers of migraines in students and found that stress affected 58% of participants, followed by lack of sleep (74.7%) and meal skipping or hunger (57.3%). A related study by Ragab et al. (2023) among intern doctors and medical students at five Egyptian universities reported

that sleep problems (94.4%) and stress (81.4%) were the primary triggers.

Migraines: Symptoms and Disability

Migraines can vary from moderate to severe, often causing significant functional disability that can interfere with students' academic lives. Pradeep et al. (2020) found that migraine severity directly impacts quality of life. In their study, participants scored an average of 66.9 on the impact of migraines and 23.43 on the Migraine Disability Assessment, with most experiencing moderate to severe disability. The study also noted that students with coexisting anxiety and depression had more frequent and longer-lasting migraines, resulting in a greater decline in quality of life (Pradeep et al., 2020).

Migraines often present with a range of debilitating symptoms. Renjith et al. (2016) found that patients reported phonophobia (85%), nausea (76.7%), vomiting (41.7%), and sleep disturbances (83.3%). About 88.3% reported that migraines affected their daily activities, with 41.7% experiencing moderate disability and 31.6% severe disability. Chronic migraines, in particular, led to more missed days from work, school, or social activities compared to episodic migraines (Renjith et al., 2016; Zaid, 2019).

Sleep disturbances were also highlighted as a significant factor in migraine disability. Sengul et al. (2015) found that 83.3% of migraine patients reported sleep problems, which were commonly linked to depression, anxiety, and excessive daytime sleepiness. Another important symptom is kinesiophobia—fear of movement due to pain—which affects physical activity and self-efficacy. Pina et al. (2024) reported that 51.1% of participants experienced kinesiophobia, which was associated with increased disability, heightened pain catastrophizing, and reduced engagement in vigorous physical activity.

Impact of Migraines on Students' Academic Performance

Migraines can negatively affect students' academic performance, potentially threatening their ability to achieve academic goals. Osman Ali et al. (2022) studied medical students at Khartoum University, Sudan, and found that migraines caused significant academic impairment. Among 109 students with migraines, 94% reported reduced study or inability to participate in daily activities for at least one day. Concentration in lectures was affected for 97.2% of students, and 98.2% reported difficulty continuing work due to fatigue. Furthermore, migraines aggravated during exam preparation, leading 33.9% of students to stop studying altogether (Osman Ali et al., 2022).

Similarly, Szabó et al. (2024) examined the impact of migraines on medical students at Alfaisal University, Saudi Arabia. Among 130 students with migraines, 66% reported that migraines were triggered by exams, and 63% experienced higher frequency of migraines during exam periods. High intensity and severity of migraines affected 59% of participants, resulting in missed

productivity for 86% of students. The study also found that migraines contributed to decreased GPAs, particularly with advancing academic years, demonstrating how migraines can undermine academic achievement over time (Elsheikh et al., 2023; Butt et al., 2024; Szabó et al., 2024).

Statement of the Problem

Migraine is a highly prevalent neurological disorder that disproportionately affects young adults, including university students, and is often accompanied by psychiatric comorbidities such as anxiety, stress, and depression. Despite its high prevalence, the combined impact of migraine and associated mental health conditions on academic performance remains underexplored, particularly in Pakistani university settings. Most existing studies focus narrowly on medical students or consider migraine and mental health in isolation, leaving critical gaps regarding how these factors interact to affect educational outcomes, including concentration, exam performance, attendance, and GPA. Additionally, little is known about the influence of migraine subtypes, especially migraine with aura, on students' psychological well-being and academic functioning. Understanding these complex interactions is essential, as untreated migraines and psychiatric symptoms can create a cycle of disability and academic impairment, potentially jeopardizing students' long-term educational and professional trajectories. Therefore, there is an urgent need to examine the prevalence of migraines, their psychiatric comorbidities, and their collective impact on academic performance among university students in Pakistan, providing evidence to inform campus health policies, support services, and targeted interventions.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it addresses critical gaps in understanding the intersection of migraine, mental health, and academic performance among university students—a population particularly vulnerable to both neurological and psychological stressors. By examining the prevalence and severity of migraines, along with associated anxiety, depression, and stress, this research provides valuable insight into how these conditions jointly impact students' academic functioning, including concentration, exam performance, and GPA. The findings of this study can inform university administrators, health services, and counseling centers about the necessity of early screening and intervention programs for students at risk of migraines and psychiatric comorbidities. Moreover, it highlights the importance of targeted mental health support, stress management strategies, and academic accommodations, which can improve students' quality of life, reduce functional impairment, and enhance educational outcomes. By focusing on both migraine subtypes (with and without aura) and the co-occurrence of psychiatric conditions, the study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the mechanisms underlying

academic difficulties among affected students. This knowledge is essential for developing culturally relevant, evidence-based interventions in Pakistan and comparable contexts, ultimately promoting student well-being, retention, and academic success.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the prevalence of migraines and common psychiatric conditions (anxiety, stress, depression) among university students.
2. To examine the co-occurrence of migraines and mental health conditions and their potential reciprocal effects.
3. To identify primary triggers of migraines and assess their impact on academic performance.
4. To provide recommendations for university health and academic support systems to mitigate the effects of migraines and associated mental health conditions.

Research Questions

1. What is the prevalence of migraines and psychiatric conditions among university students?
2. To what extent do migraines co-occur with anxiety, stress, and depression?
3. What are the main triggers of migraines, and how do they affect students' academic performance?
4. What strategies can universities implement to support students affected by migraines and related mental health issues?

Methodology

Population

The target population for this study consisted of undergraduate and graduate students enrolled at FATA University and Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology. Students from all academic years, ranging from first-year to senior-year students, were considered, representing diverse faculties and disciplines, including sciences, arts, and professional studies.

Sampling Method and Sample Size

A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure proportional representation across faculties, academic years, and gender, providing a balanced and generalizable sample reflective of the university student population. A total of 412 students participated, including 218 females (53%) and 194 males (47%), ensuring adequate gender representation for examining potential differences in migraine prevalence and mental health conditions. The sample size was determined based on prior prevalence studies and the desired level of statistical power.

Inclusion Criteria

- Enrolled as a full-time student at FATA University or Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology.
- Aged between 18 and 30 years.
- Willing to provide informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Students with a diagnosed chronic neurological disorder other than migraine.
- Students unwilling to complete the survey or provide consent.

Data Collection

All Participants were recruited voluntarily, invited through email invitations that included digital flyers. Data were collected using Google Forms, an online survey platform. Demographic information such as age, gender, ethnicity, academic year, and field of study was recorded. All data were collected directly by the researcher using the methods described above.

Instruments

Several validated instruments were used to assess the relationships between mental health, migraines, and academic performance:

- **Migraine Disability Assessment (MIDAS):** Measured the impact of migraines on productivity and daily activities over the previous three months, including severity of pain and functional limitations (Stewart et al., 2001).
- **ID Migraine Test:** Identified migraines through three questions evaluating light sensitivity, nausea, and functional impairment (Lipton et al., 2003).
- **Perceived Stress Scale (PSS):** Assessed participants' perceived stress levels and psychological responses to life events, with scores ranging from 0 to 4, including reverse-coded items (Cohen et al., 1983).
- **Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7):** Screened for generalized anxiety symptoms experienced over the last two weeks (Spitzer et al., 1999).
- **Patient Health Questionnaire-4 (PHQ-4):** Evaluated depression and anxiety, with scores ranging from 0 to 12, indicating levels from mild to severe (Kroenke et al., 2009).

Custom survey questions were included to assess the academic consequences of migraines, including effects on studying, exam preparation, and overall productivity. The **ICHD-3 Diagnostic Criteria** (Headache Classification Committee of the International Headache Society, 2018) was used to evaluate migraine symptoms and identify aura migraines.

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic characteristics and prevalence rates. Chi-square tests and one-way ANOVA were applied to examine associations between mental health variables, migraine prevalence, and academic performance. A significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ was used for all inferential tests.

Findings

The study examined the prevalence of migraines, mental health conditions, and their impact on academic performance among 412 university students from FATA University and Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology.

Prevalence of Migraines and Mental Health Issues

- Migraines were reported by 118 students (28.5%).
- Anxiety was observed in 132 students (32%), depression in 119 (28.9%), and stress in 107 (26%).
- Co-occurrence of migraines and psychiatric conditions was notable: 74 students (18%) had migraines with anxiety, and 68 students (16.5%) had migraines with depression.
- Gender breakdown revealed slightly higher prevalence of migraines among females (62%) compared to males (38%). Anxiety and depression also had higher prevalence among females (anxiety: 56%, depression: 54%) than males.

Correlation Between Migraines and Mental Health

- Chi-square analysis showed students with anxiety were 2.4 times more likely to report migraines ($p = 0.001$), while those with depression were 1.9 times more likely ($p = 0.004$).
- Stress emerged as the most common migraine trigger, reported by 71% of affected students, followed by lack of sleep (65%) and academic workload (58%).

Impact of Migraines on Academic Performance

- Among students with migraines: 66 (56%) reported reduced concentration, 50 (42%) missed at least one exam, 72 (61%) experienced GPA decline, 48 (41%) missed lectures, and 70 (59%) faced difficulty completing assignments.
- Students with coexisting anxiety or depression experienced more frequent and severe migraines, further exacerbating academic difficulties.

Table 1: Prevalence of Migraines and Mental Health Conditions (N = 412)

Condition	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Migraine	118	28.5
Anxiety	132	32.0
Depression	119	28.9
Stress	107	26.0
Coexisting Migraine & Anxiety	74	18.0
Coexisting Migraine & Depression	68	16.5

Table 2: Correlation of Migraines with Mental Health Conditions

Mental Health Condition	Migraine Yes	Migraine No	Odds Ratio (OR)	p-value
Anxiety	74	58	2.40	0.001
Depression	68	51	1.90	0.004
Stress	77	30	3.10	<0.001

Table 3: Academic Impact of Migraines

Academic Outcome	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Reduced concentration in class	66	56
Missed exams or assessments	50	42
GPA decline reported	72	61
Missed lectures	48	41

Discussion

The findings demonstrate that migraines are a prevalent health concern among university students and are closely associated with anxiety, depression, and stress. Stress emerged as the most significant trigger for migraine attacks, consistent with prior research indicating a bidirectional relationship between migraine and psychological conditions (Bergman-Bock, 2017; Rafi et al., 2022). Female students exhibited higher prevalence rates for both migraines and mental health conditions, aligning with global trends in migraine epidemiology and mental health vulnerability (Oedegaard et al., 2006; Birkie et al., 2021).

The study also highlighted the academic consequences of migraines. Reduced concentration, missed exams, GPA decline, and difficulty completing assignments were commonly reported among students experiencing migraines, especially those with comorbid psychiatric conditions. These results reinforce the notion that migraines, when compounded by mental health issues, create a cumulative burden that negatively impacts academic achievement and overall student well-being (Osman Ali et al., 2022; Szabó et al., 2024).

Recommendations**1. University Health Services and Counseling:**

- Implement screening programs for migraines and mental health conditions.
- Provide accessible counseling services, stress management workshops, and peer support groups for students.

2. Academic Policies and Educational Interventions:

- Develop flexible academic policies such as extensions or makeup exams for students affected by migraines.
- Raise awareness among students and faculty about the connection between migraines, stress, and mental health.

3. Preventive and Lifestyle Strategies:

- Offer workshops on sleep hygiene, time management, and coping mechanisms to reduce stress-related migraines.
- Encourage regular physical activity, short study breaks, and balanced nutrition to prevent migraine triggers.

4. Future Research:

- Conduct longitudinal studies to examine how migraines and psychiatric comorbidities evolve across academic years.
- Investigate biological, social, and psychological mechanisms linking migraines with mental health issues.
- Compare findings across multiple universities in Pakistan to develop culturally relevant interventions.

5. Policy Implications:

- Integrate mental health and migraine management programs into university wellness initiatives.
- Foster collaboration between academic departments,

health centers, and counseling services to support students holistically.

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